

Figure S1: a) SEM image of a-SNOM probe glued to the tuning fork with the b) detail.

Figure S2: Photoluminescence (PL) of CsPbBr₃ NCs measured using a-SNOM for the approached (0-20 nm above the sample) and retracted (1 μm above the sample) positions of the a-SNOM probe.

Figure S3: Dependence of PL spectral full width at half maximum (FWHM) and amplitude on the entrance slit width of the spectrometer used for PL detection in the a-SNOM setup. As the slit width increases, the PL amplitude increases due to improved light throughput, while the spectral FWHM broadens due to reduced spectral resolution. The PL amplitude varies with the probe position, reflecting

local emission intensity, whereas the FWHM remains independent of the a-SNOM tip position, indicating that spectral resolution is primarily governed by slit width rather than near-field probe effects.

Figure S4: Consecutive near-field (NF) measurements confirming the absence of photo-induced changes during scanning. (Top row a-c) Topography, PL intensity, and PL lifetime maps of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals acquired in the first NF scan. (Bottom row d-f) Corresponding maps of the same region obtained immediately afterward under identical excitation conditions (407 nm, 0.2 μW). Both scans exhibit nearly identical spatial features and absolute intensity/lifetime distributions, confirming the stability of the sample and the absence of local photobleaching, heating, or degradation during measurement.

Figure S5: NF PL intensity map recorded simultaneously with PL lifetime data acquisition during the a-SNOM scan. The image shows the integrated PL signal detected by the avalanche photodiode. This raw intensity map corresponds to the total photon counts across the entire temporal window and was extracted directly from the same dataset used for lifetime fitting. The spatial features closely match those in the NF PL map shown in Figure 3b, confirming that the detected signal reflects genuine sample emission rather than tip-related artifacts.

Figure S6: Time-resolved PL (TRPL) of CsPbBr₃ NCs measured using a-SNOM with the approached and retracted (1 μm above the sample) positions of the a-SNOM probe. When the probe is approached, the PL decay is less noisy, indicating enhanced signal collection due to near-field enhancement.

Figure S7: Residuals from single-exponential fits of TRPL decay curves shown in Figure 4b and 4d. Residuals are plotted for the selected spatial positions marked in the PL lifetime maps (black, green, purple, blue, and red points). Each trace represents the difference between the experimental data and the corresponding fitted curve, normalized to the maximum PL count.

Figure S8: The rest of the correlation analysis of maps obtained using a-SNOM, including topography, PL, and TRPL. Red points highlight topographic features exceeding 100 nm in height.